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Data Set (DS) OPR Published Externally	<p>Acropora retusa</p> <p>Specific areas of critical habitat for the Indo-Pacific coral species <i>Acropora retusa</i> include marine area around 5 island units in American Samoa (Tutuila, Ofu & Olosega, Ta'u, Rose Atoll, and Swains) with suitable hard-bottom habitat within the depth range 0-20 m, as described below. Specific areas of critical habitat were delineated in four steps: (1) General information was used to delineate...</p> <p> View Hierarchy InPort XML ISO 19115 </p>
Data Set (DS) OPR Published Externally	<p>Acropora retusa coral species critical habitat for use in ESA/FIFRA consultations</p> <p>These data represent critical habitat designated (July 15, 2025) under the Endangered Species Act for the coral <i>Acropora retusa</i> at 5 island units in American Samoa (Tutuila, Ofu & Olosega, Ta'u, Rose Atoll, and Swains). Please refer to the Code of Federal Regulations and the supporting information report for more details and consider the regulatory language when using these spatial data. htt...</p> <p> View Hierarchy InPort XML ISO 19115 </p>

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